
RELIGIOUS TOURISM AND ITS ROLE IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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Annotation: The article analyzes the development processes of religious and pilgrimage tourism, the factors and conditions affecting it, shows how important it is today, gives an understanding of the problems and their solutions in this field.

Key words: Religion, social effect, religious tourism, pilgrimage tourism, mausoleums.

DINIY TURIZM VA UNING TURIZM SOHASIDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada diniy va ziyorat turizmining rivojlanish jarayonlari, unga ta’sir etuvchi omillar va shart-sharoitlar tahlil qilinadi va hozirgi kunda qay darajada ahamyat kasb etishi haqida to’xtalib o’tiladi, bu soha bilan bog’liq muammolar va ularning yechimlari haqida tushuncha beriladi.

Kalit so’zlar: Din, ijtimoiy ta’sir, diniy turizm, ziyorat turizmi, maqbaralar.

РЕЛИОЗНЫЙ ТУРИЗМ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В ТУРИЗМЕ

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Аннотация: В статье анализируются процессы развития религиозного и паломнического туризма, факторы и условия, влияющие на него, показывается его значимость сегодня, дается понимание проблем, связанных с этой сферой, и путей их решения.

Ключевые слова: Религия, влияние общества, религиозный туризм, паломнический туризм, мавзолеи.

Tourism encompasses the activities of people traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for leisure, business, or other purposes. It's a multifaceted industry involving various aspects like transportation, accommodation, attraction, religion and experiences.

Religious tourism is one of the oldest forms of tourism, and represents a significant, evolving, growing, and increasingly diverse sector of the global tourism market. Religious tourism, a powerful blend of faith and travel, has captivated individuals for centuries. From pilgrimages to sacred sites to visits to architectural marvels steeped in religious history, this unique form of tourism offers a profound experience that transcends mere sightseeing. Religious tourism divided into 2 main types:

- pilgrimage tourism
- excursion and educational religious tourism.

Today more than 200 million people around the world visit various places that are sacred to them. According to statistics, 45 million Muslims, 150 million Christians,

and 40 million Buddhists travel on pilgrimage (N. Bozorov, 2022). Many people in the world travel to Makkah, the holy land of Vatican temples and other places. Samarkand and Bukhara are the places where such holy pilgrimages are made in Uzbekistan. Historical monuments located in Khorazm and other regions of our country are an example. In particular, Imam al-Bukhari shrine, which is considered a small pilgrimage for the Muslim world, has an important place in the development of religious tourism.

In the tourism market, there are services for trips to Finland and other Scandinavian and Western European countries to celebrate Christmas and other holidays. A trip to Rovaniemi, the homeland of Santa Claus, located on the polar border of Finland, is becoming especially popular among tourists. Here celebrations are held for children and adults. A modern airport has been built in Lapland, and even planes fly there. Shows with the participation of Santa Claus and gnomes are organized for guests, a supermarket is built in the village of a Santa Claus, and children's theaters are built in the caves.

Religious tourism can have significant economic and sociocultural impacts on destinations:

-Revenue Generation: Religious tourism generates income for local communities through accommodation, transportation, food services, souvenirs, and donations to religious institutions.

-Employment Creation: The tourism industry associated with religious sites creates job opportunities in various sectors, including hospitality, transportation, and cultural heritage management.

-Infrastructure Development: Increased tourism can lead to improvements in infrastructure, such as transportation networks, accommodation facilities, and visitor amenities.

- Intercultural Dialogue: Religious can promote understanding respect between different faith communities and cultures.
- Preservation of Heritage: Tourism revenue can support the conservation and restoration of religious sites and cultural artifacts.
- Community Development: Religious tourism can empower local communities, fostering entrepreneurship and cultural preservation initiatives.
- Commodification of Religion: Concerns exist regarding the potential commodification of religious experiences and the need to balance economic benefits with respect for sacred spaces and traditions.

Religious tourism is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon with profound economic, sociocultural, and environmental implications. Understanding the motivations of religious travelers, managing the impacts on destinations, and promoting sustainable practices are essential for ensuring the long-term viability and positive contributions of this growing sector within the global tourism industry. Further research is needed to explore the evolving dynamics of religious tourism, address emerging challenges, and harness its potential to foster intercultural understanding, spiritual growth, and sustainable development.

REFERENCES

1. Nuralibek Bozorov, "Ziyorat turizmi tarixi va uning turizm sohasida tutgan o'rni",2022.
2. "Turizm asoslari", O'quv qo'llanma.
3. Xoliqnazarov Ubaydulloh, "O'zbekistonda diniy turizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari",2023.